

Textualisation of Sexual Harassment on the Cameroonian University Campus: Analysis of Moone Nda'a's *La révolte de Mbazoua et autres nouvelles*

Albert Jiatsa Jokeng

Université de Maroua, Maroua, Cameroon

jiatsajiokeng_al@yahoo.fr

Translated by Georgina Collins

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Abstract

Fictional representations of African university campuses offer a rather dismal image of a world intended to train the intellectual elite of a rapidly developing continent. This is reflected in a statement from Jean-Marie Wounfa, who asserted: “Writers, for a long time, have put forward a discourse on the university that praises and preserves the mythical character of this institution of which the representation is abundantly watered at the spring of the collective unconscious.” But such a position fails to win unanimous support. Some consider the university to be a depraved institution. While such discourse may find a fertile ground in the novel, it becomes an interesting scriptural paradigm when the analytical medium shifts to the short story, a brief but dense literary genre inspired by reality. Such an image of the Cameroonian university campus can be seen in *La révolte de Mbazoua* (Mbazoua's Rebellion) by Moone Nda'a, which describes the campus as a Kafkaesque world haunted by intimidation, rape, threatening behaviour, sectarianism and other ills that students and teachers must suffer. It also highlights the role of the imaginary in the struggle against this form of censorship that shackles the harmonious development of the African university campus.

Keywords

Sexual harassment; university campuses in Cameroon; new; Moone Nda'a; censorship in Cameroon

Introduction

Sexual harassment is no new topic in the field of academic literary studies, but when this issue becomes a profound scriptural paradigm in the writings of academics, it deserves to be analysed as such. Moone Nda'a's *La révolte de Mbazoua* (Mbazoua's Rebellion) is a collection of short stories featuring the eponymous heroine, published in 2020 by Éditions Ifrikiya, based in Yaoundé, Cameroon. It depicts Cameroonian university campuses as Augean stables dominated by intimidation, rape, threatening behaviour, sectarianism and other ills that students and sometimes teachers must endure. This study describes an unstable situation in which censorship and *omertà* propel university populations into different forms of trauma. It further elucidates the imagination's role in the fight against "the unsaid", caused by this censorship hindering the harmonious development of Cameroonian university campuses. The majority of sub-Saharan African universities emerged after the wave of independence in the 1960s. As such, the influence of politics has not strayed far from their administration. Despite the tremendous qualitative leap they represent in terms of the wider world's global development, the inherited weight of that era continues to keep them at the bottom of global university league tables. Nevertheless, they became a forum for a multitude of demands, having steered many countries towards an improved form of democracy thanks to the Easterly Wind of 1990.¹ In terms of literature, Moone Nda'a's collection of short stories, *La révolte de Mbazoua*, stands out for its impact in terms of satire, which it uses to denounce the failings that continue to plague universities. In its critique of universities, how does the imaginary – and the short story in particular – align with the expression "The Shameful State" (Labou Tansi)? How can the choice of this literary genre be interpreted as a mode of expression used to describe the university *Lebenswelt*?² The answer to these questions lies principally³ in the utilisation of the theoretical-methodological postulates of Christiane Lahaie (1998), who proposes an exegesis of the short story's discourse based on four key points: "fragmented writing"; "the unsaid, 'paralogical' discourse"; "compensation through precision"; and "a beginning in media res". An exploration of the collection's intertextual framework will serve to strengthen Lahaie's insights, showing the author's care in connecting his text to others, thus forming a library as defined by Sophie Rabau (2002).⁴ Finally, Vincent Jouve's theory on the character effect (1992) completes the methodological framework. This theoretical outline helps define the short story's critical role in the context of discourse on Cameroonian universities.

Poetics of a Socially Engaged Genre: The Aesthetic Pillars of *La révolte de Mbazoua*

What gives the short story its distinctive quality as a genre related to the novel is its particular use of narrative techniques. While the pliability of text in the novel allows writers to turn to lengthy digressions, commentaries and descriptions, in the short story, everything done is essential, making room for impact. To this end, the short story collection by Moone Nda'a⁵ expresses a discourse inscribed in a field of human activity. Indeed, Dominique Maingueneau (1996, 28) believes that any discourse is located in a discursive field (bourgeois, proletarian, communist, surrealist, religious, secular, etc.). Here, the key text, *La révolte de Mbazoua*, is a university discourse. A short introduction to this short story collection helps set the scene. *La révolte de Mbazoua* is a collection of tales providing an insight into university life. There are five texts in the collection, three of which will be discussed in this article: “La révolte de Mbazoua”, “L’aventure de Tatisong ou la fin du mirage américain” (The Adventures of Tatisong or the End of the American Dream), and “Agnès ou les frissons des rues de Maritzburg” (Agnès or the Chills of Maritzburg Streets). In fact, Moone Nda'a portrays a university environment heavily characterised by sexual harassment and the rape of female students by teachers, with some female students awarded bad marks at the end of their studies when they make their opposition to this clear. This is what happens to Mbazoua, a naïve young student who has recently arrived from her village only to find herself ensnared by lecturers Ndingo and Mvenfa. Raped many times in a dark office on campus, she remains silent until the day she takes her revenge. It is also a collection that introduces us to the deplorable working conditions of Tatisong, a temporary lecturer at the university. I previously noted this aspect of the abusive exploitation of teachers in my educational essay *La condition de l’enseignant vacataire* (The Conditions of Temporary Lecturers; Jokeng 2015). Likewise, the situation is hardly fantastic for employed lecturers, who crumble beneath the weight of such deplorable conditions, portrayed by Antoine-Beauvard Zanga in his latest novel, *Tais-toi et enseigne* (Shut Up and Teach; 2019), and by Ernest Chuinteu in *Professeur malgré lui: à la quête de l’école nouvelle* (Teacher, Despite Himself: Searching for a New School; 2019). Compared with the protagonists in these texts, Tatisong is practically unpaid; he is exploited by his university and must be content with the privilege of teaching for free.⁶ He faces situations where merit is worth nothing before nepotism and inside influence. Moone Nda'a also tells us about the risky situations that teachers face once they manage to obtain academic mobility, becoming researchers in host countries. Agnès and Roger, characters in the short story “Agnès ou les frissons des rues de Maritzburg”, live from

day to day in fear of being assaulted on the streets of South Africa, because, despite the official end of apartheid in 1990, a sense of race segregation still prevails over 30 years later. Scenes depicting the university sometimes take place “in the corridors of the Faculty of Arts and Literature” (Nda’a 2020, 9), at other times “at the University”, and more precisely “at Maroua University” (ibid., 33).⁷ The diegetic context of these stories as they unfold therefore revolves around university campuses. But the detail revealed is not homogeneous; rather, it resembles a macro-story consisting of *mises-en-abîme*, micro-stories, a sort of puzzle, “stories with holes” that the reader must fill in during the reading process. This is what drives Lahaie to consider the short story to be a fragmentary piece of writing. And Moone Nda’a heavily exploits this scriptural technique. For Lahaie, fragmentary writing is where “information is only revealed in snippets, as if it were a matter of solving a puzzle bit by bit” (1998, 63). This is justified by the fact that “through its brevity, the short story could not comprise a plot in its entirety”. This precision reaffirms an idea conveyed by Doseline Kiguru, who draws upon the views of Nadine Gordimer in reference to short stories, maintaining that the genre is “more malleable and open to experimentation with style, language and form than the novel, which means that it is more easily accommodated within a variety of media spaces” (Kiguru 2020, 37).

La révolte de Mbazoua is a collection of short stories that can be read unconnected. In the context of fragmented writing such as this, Gérard Genette (1972) made a distinction between the telling (the oral or written discourse that introduces a plot) of a story (the subject of the telling, what it recounts) and the narration (the telling’s productive act, which, as such, is responsible for technical choices like the type of narrator or the order in which elements of a story are told). While the discourse of this collection is one that is of/about universities, its story is that of a character who acquires various positions across the different texts. Thus, in each story with a university focus, the question of who is telling the story poses a problem of voice within the relevant text. The narrator – distinct from the author – is the one who tells the story. And the narrator can take different forms, whether absent from the story itself or appearing within it as a character.

A Story in the First Person: The Autobiographical/Autodiegetic Short Story

The position of the narrator is always meaningful in any tale, especially in “autobiographical short stories”, where author, narrator and character in the story are one and the same person. For example, take the narrator-character Tatisong in the short story “L’aventure de

Tatissong ou la fin du mirage américain” (Nda’a 2020, 21), who tells the true story⁸ of the author, Moone Nda’a, on American and South African soil; the same narrative position can be seen in “Agnès ou les frissons des rues de Maritzburg” (ibid., 47). The relevant character in this short story is called Roger:⁹ “While Roger drifted further into his daydream ...” (ibid., 52). For Moone Nda’a, the use of this “narrative instance” pertains to personal involvement, participation in events reported, and the author’s testimony of his university experiences. This is what we call an autobiographical/autodiegetic tale. The same can be said for the narrator of the short story “La révolte de Mbazoua”, who, by “razing the walls and listening at doors” (ibid., 9), happens to come across Mbazoua’s story, which he then offers to tell us, because, according to him, “one story always looks to another and so on, to the point where at any given moment, the sum of stories drawn from every direction takes the vague appearance of a mosaic” (ibid., 12). It is thus his responsibility to relate these facts as a witness to the story. The narrator has the same status in the third short story when he extricates himself from the tale: “Agnès was the one to point it out to me, not without begging us to agree to accompany her home because, she said, she’s not accustomed to returning after 5 pm” (ibid., 47). The personal involvement of the author in these three short stories therefore strengthens the narrator’s autobiographical/autodiegetic position.

The Practice of Intertextuality

Further to this, the interplay between texts reinforces the fragmentary writing. This type of writing is consistent with “modern consciousness” as proposed by Nadine Gordimer, who believes that short story writing is “a fragmented and restless form, a matter of hit or miss, and it is perhaps for this reason that it suits modern consciousness” (2010, 170–171). While Roland Barthes states that “any text is an intertext” (1973, 999), in the context of this short story collection, it is also about conscious, non-random choice: the reference to the *Vacatorium* (26, 28) relates to another essay focusing on the stark analysis of Cameroonian university campuses. *La Condition de l’enseignant vacataire: In Vacatorium* (The Conditions of the Temporary Lecturer: In Temporarium) is a 2015 educative essay in which I developed the same theses, describing a limping, corrupt and mafia-like education system in Cameroon. This title invites readers to cast aside their famed idleness to take ownership of this short introductory text, and to understand other situations that could not be enumerated in the context of the short story. The same applies to the term “Mont Plaisant” (Mount Pleasant; Nda’a 2020, 30), which refers to the historical novel by Patrice Nganang about Sultan Njoya.

And then there are characters such as “Neni” (ibid., 42) “Madame Edwards” (ibid., 43) and “Jende” (ibid., 43), who are taken from the bestselling novel *Behold the Dreamers* by Imbolo Mbue and who give tangible form to Tatisong’s adventures in the country of Uncle Sam. Hence, intertextuality ensures that, depending on their degree of knowledge and past reading, each person picking up the book can establish for him- or herself the links between former texts and this collection, thereby creating a “library” – as defined by Sophie Rabau – from this short story collection.

The Unsaid: The “Paralogical” Discourse of Moone Nda’a

“Paralogical” discourse and discourse “beside things” are terms used by Michel Lord (1993) to explain how short stories beat around the bush to lull the reader to sleep and best prepare them for the final revelation. Since short stories select elements to describe (though, in reality, all writing is selective), unlike novels, they cannot express all details needed for the reader to have a global view of the story being told. Lahaie puts it like this:

Because it cannot say everything, the short story holds back certain pieces of information. Needless to say, short story writers, male or female, will eliminate all facts that may not be indispensable. But beyond that inevitability, a writer may decide to hide a clue and not reveal it until the end of the text (the well-known “twist”, found in many short stories); this is called the unsaid. The entire strength of the unsaid lies precisely in the fact that certain elements of a plot (the gender of the narrative authority or the identity of the main character, for example) are more beneficial being hidden rather than revealed. The twist, that surprise produced at the end of a text, thus serves, at the very last moment, to hit the reader, who will not have been attentive enough to the seemingly trivial details also provided by the novelist. When Michel Lord speaks of “paralogical” discourse, discourse “beside things”, he explains how the short story beats around the bush to send readers to sleep and best prepares them for the final revelation. (Lahaie 1998, 64)

So, what is unsaid in the short stories here? Moone Nda’a does not mention real-life events at Cameroonian universities. The unsaid in this section relates to the “unsaid” of a society that Moone Nda’a says to be otherwise – thus confronting the unsaid due to censorship. The same applies to literary and artistic censorship, an administrative or political act consisting of examining the quality of the mind’s creations before allowing them to be published or shown.

This censorship is thus supposed to function upstream of literary publication. However, with the exorbitant number of literary outputs taking advantage of how easy it is to write and publish books in Cameroon,¹⁰ censorship has shifted the monopoly of its action downstream – in other words, towards reception. Hence, it is mostly practised after the publication of a piece of work. This type of censorship avoids external concerns regarding freedom of expression because it is implemented in a more sibylline way when scheduling works, selecting scholarships, developing school curricula, etc. Furthermore, it is founded on an arsenal of internal campus rules that prevent many individuals from expressing themselves openly. Censorship is therefore the main unsaid, denounced by the author who develops a pinboard of subcategories for this “soft” form of censorship.

- **Sexual harassment and rape:** The two terms often come together because one frequently leads to the other. The expression NST¹¹ is well known in universities. It can refer to a female student who offers a teacher sex for unwarranted grades (this situation is rare for male students), or a teacher who capitalises on their position as part of the teaching body by having sex (consensual or forced) with a student they desire. Although the university’s ethical code may crack down on this, the majority of victims keep quiet for lack of obvious proof, because they are frightened of rumours spreading or their case being dismissed. *La révolte de Mbazoua* (Nda’a 2020, 9, 10) thus opens on a rape scene in Professor Ndingo’s office: “Mbazoua, her navy blue short-sleeved shirt crumpled at the bust suggested the presence of villainous hands. Her ripped knickers were hanging in shreds over her pretty thighs.” As a village girl with the misfortune to be beautiful, she suffers the acts of her supervisor in silence, for fear of being humiliated. Her supervisor does not reach out to her gently: “he furiously impaled her, again and again and again” (ibid., 15). Always intimidating, “he raped her as often as he could and, each time, he left the same threatening behaviour to linger upon her” (ibid., 17). This sort of occurrence has been frequently and widely talked about on Cameroonian university campuses. We cannot put ourselves at risk in universities, microcosms of the city, real-life Augean stables that even Hercules could not clean. (Incidentally, the author does not speak about this in his stories but knows that most readers will comprehend or else assume.)
- **Omertà:** A notion expressing both the code of silence peculiar to the mafia and the unspoken solidarity of the student and/or teaching body vis-à-vis acts of sexual

misconduct. Information is known and yet no one speaks out. This is understandable from the perspective of persecutors but not from the viewpoint of victims. Abused in this way, Mbazoua confides in her friends, Eugénie, Eulalie and Iphigénie, “and they all tell her the same thing: endure, tolerate, obtain her master’s and leave. They all have the same story to tell, bear the same sorrow. One of being at the mercy of certain lecturers partial to sex and who, with neither elegance nor courtesy, abused them, always with the one and only sword of Damocles: failure and bad grades” (ibid., 13–14).

- **The working conditions of teachers:** Their conditions depend on recruitment processes, salary, nomination and even sponsorship of the teacher. Recruitment to Cameroonian universities is normally carried out in each department of the faculty and according to regulations. Nevertheless, politics often gain a foothold in departments when there is a lecturer recruitment drive at the university. Such is the case for Tatisong, a character in the short story “L’aventure de Tatisong ou la fin du mirage américain” (ibid., 21). Indeed, in a conversation with his wife Adélaïde, he declares, “Did you forget the government launched a massive recruitment drive for lecturers in higher education: the 1,000?” (ibid., 27). It is relevant to note here that the 9 March 2011 press release regarding the “Special recruitment of 25,000 young graduates to the Public Service in the 2011 financial year”, signed by Emmanuel Bondé, the Minister of Public Service and Administrative Reform, in article 31, set a recruitment quota of 1,000 teaching personnel out of those 25,000 young civil servants, thus flouting the university’s traditional recruitment processes. But how much are Cameroonian academics paid? The salary of a Cameroonian academic ranges from €534 to €800 per month,¹² which is not enough for lecturers to have the standard of living and working required to carry out research and teaching (especially in a country where the cost of living is very high, where almost everything is imported, where every opinion is politicised and can lead to incarceration, and where denunciation and official tribalism continue to rage as the government has never taken a position on them). That is why Tatisong ends up being morally corrupted by the idea of immigration and the temptation of the American dream. His adventure is one doomed to fail, for, after 365 days’ holiday, he cannot tolerate an American world based on cultural norms completely opposite to his own. Like Jende, the hero in Mbue’s novel to which he alludes, Tatisong ends up returning to Cameroon.

Furthermore, the appointment to a post of responsibility confers benefits on some teachers that they often abuse: Professor Ndingo was one of those who “had started at the university thanks to a nomination” (ibid., 16). As head of department, he also had an office-cum-theatre for sleazy extracurricular activities.

This paralogical discourse is related to *satura*. In its first sense, *satura* is a popular dish made from diverse and varied ingredients. Its meaning in literature is that of a particular genre, specifically one that features a blend of prose and verse, as well as a playful treatment of various subjects that are frequently trivial or banal. Etymologically, *satura* refers to a “play in verse combining various metres, a sort of farce that mocks a person or situation” (Van Gorp et al. 2005, 437). It is a piece of work where the objective is a derisory critique of its subject, with the aim of inciting some sort of change. Quintilien (X, 1, 9) claims that “*satura tota nostra est*” (satire is wholly ours). He thus maintains that satire is a Latin creation where the definition proper is a “potpourri” characterised by flexibility of subject, tone, rhythm and length. Moone Nda’a employs paralogical discourse such as satire to:

- reduce the significance of such abuses on university campuses to make them seem ridiculous;
- exaggerate, a common technique in satire, where a real situation is inflated to make it ridiculous – caricatures are used as part of this technique;
- juxtapose and compare things of unequal significance (by means of elevated intertextuality), so that both assume the lowest level of importance; and
- parody – imitating the behaviour and style of a person, place or thing to ridicule them.

In short, satire gives rise to considerable freedom of speech, encouraging the use of critical and derisory vocabulary. It provides a space for liberty, extricated from constraints of style, genre, ideology, etc. Strictly speaking, satire can be found only in preserved literature: the Horatian “sermons”, the Satires of Lucilius, Juvenal and Persius, as well as Menippean and Varronian satire. The full weight of satire can therefore be applied to a short story.

Compensating Through Precision and Writing/Reading in Media Res

This aspect of writing relates to the literary artifice particular to every short story writer:

The composition of a short story, however brief it may be, can end up being the place for particularly fertile lexical and syntactical research. Finding the right word, the appropriate turn of phrase, takes on increased importance owing to the impact the very least amount of information can exert within the text of a short story. (Lahaie 1998, 64)

Thanks to its brevity, each short story is densified and each word conveys a number of hints and assumptions. The same can be said for the realistic, coded university language that, in the linguistic enunciation of these short stories, accurately informs their spatio-temporal context: referring to “the 1,000” (Nda’a 2020, 27) underpins an entire string of information about the recruitment of teachers in higher education, which sparked a bitter controversy regarding wages, mafia-like recruitment networks, all types of influence, etc. This information is corroborated by a series of precise lexemes that Moone Nda’a makes a point of inserting into the text: “My friend, you are intelligent. You are even very bright, but you will never be recruited by a university. Where in the world? The land of Popol? Can you even hear the sound of your own name, man?” (ibid., 24). “Popol” is a caricature name given to Cameroon’s president by an artist at *Le Popoli* newspaper. This written representation of reality then takes shape by referring to “Mont Plaisant” (ibid., 30) and its famous “Château” (Castle), which, for students, is a popular destination opposite the University of Yaoundé I, a place of depravity, bars and scheming of all sorts alongside students’ regular lives. The Château refers to a massive basin made of reinforced concrete and filled with water destined for consumption by those people in Yaoundé who overlook the hill. Over time, the meaning of the term has changed to refer to the whole district, not to glorify the basin, but to express students’ particular state of mind: while they are silenced in lecture theatres at the foot of the hill, in Château, in bars and other dark locales, they have a feeling of domination.

Moone Nda’a’s short stories begin in media res, meaning readers must interpret and complete the stories, thus involving themselves in the action. The short story is a basic text that forgoes digressions, commentaries and other constructions inflated in the novel and other literary genres. Lahaie provides more information on this:

Writing a short story imposes a separation from the ethos of the novel, which, slowly, instates the different components of its plot. The short story does not care for long descriptions, eloquent and detailed depictions, sometimes pointless and at other times spirited dialogues often stretching out over a number of pages. One small thing to make it easier: never begin revealing the plot from the start. When readers begin a short story,

they must find themselves amidst the action as soon as possible. I often advise my students to cross out the first three pages of their text but keep the last paragraph. And they start again from there ... While this experience generates considerable frustration, it soon opens the door to a degree of ingenious and surprising narrative possibilities.

Furthermore, contrary to popular belief, short stories do not just tell a brief anecdote; they must do so with a maximum level of intensity. Thus, at a push, a good short story should incite critique that is longer than the short story itself. It must encourage or re-encourage debate, awaken the imagination, stimulate the senses, stir up emotion. To do so, there needs to be a central event, an ordeal, a statement, a decision, that the reader will have to go through, to do, to experience with the character. (Lahaie 1998, 64)

Moone Nda'a places the reader in the story as it is happening. The reader meets the character Mbazoua when she is already entangled in her dealings with Professor Ndingo: there is no traditional opening as frequently seen in the novel where the character, unknown as yet, must be subjected to an often highly intense physical description.¹³ The same can be said for the character Tatisong. The location of a character in a story as well as the number of times they appear¹⁴ are always very significant.

These observations are highly relevant to long texts such as novels. In the context of the short story, however, they are concise, sometimes non-existent. The narrative outline does not offer up a standard framework, insofar as the reader does not instantly perceive the opening situation, the perturbing element of the stories studied here. Can a story beginning in the middle come to an end? This means that Moone Nda'a does not purport to conclude his short stories, but aims to interpret, finish storylines, be involved in the problems posed so as to contribute significantly to their resolutions.

Moone Nda'a's Social Writing Project

The defining feature of short stories is that they are open to every possibility. Moone Nda'a troubles the reader by painting a black picture of Cameroonian universities. He thus offers an instant and complete view of "the unsaid, the inexpressible, the painful impossibility of coinciding [what one wants to say] with reality, which will also fall short of, or beyond [what one says]" (Lahaie 1998, 64). Aside from this textualisation of universities' defects, Nda'a's work situates the role of the imagination. Every writer establishes a specific social agenda in their writing. And, despite this being his first foray, the author almost jumps at the chance to

impose his voice in a multitude of ways. The choice of the short story is thus crucial here. But it must be recognised that literary genres do not all enjoy the same success or have the same prestige. Every generation, every society, adds value to specific genres and scorns others, for reasons inherent in consumer preference. Hence, there is a hierarchy of literary genres, contrasting “noble” with “minor” genres, “scholarly” with “popular” genres, and “literature” with “paraliterature” or even “under-literature”. Inspired by antiquity, for example, French Classicism (around 1650) appreciated theatrical tragedy and disdained the novel, often written and read by women. These days, the novel is the dominant genre in Europe and Africa, but serious literary studies shun popular genres such as spy novels or romance novels (airport fiction).

The *nouvellier* (short story writer) Moone Nda’a is a man living in a time and place that is historically located. He was born in Cameroon in 1977 and since 2012 has worked as a lecturer-researcher at the University of Maroua in the Far North. For this reason, he sees himself as an objective witness to his referential world. His collection of short stories puts forward a social agenda constituting an aesthetic, moral and political message (here we are talking of educative politics): decontaminating university campuses through rules and regulations that give a new impression of this centre of knowledge.

Moreover, in Africa – and in Cameroon in particular – reading has taken a back seat owing to the shift of interest from the textual to the virtual. People watch more films, enthuse over social media, endlessly enjoy hit music from all over the world. Faced with this flood of media, writing has had to reinvent itself to increase its appeal. This reinvention runs through the whole aesthetic of the short story, which moves instantly to the indispensable, providing information without embellishment, without accompanying discourse that sometimes makes the text long and fatigues the reader. Moone Nda’a understands that. Considering the failure of the literary establishment when faced with the exponential rise of new information and communication technologies,¹⁵ which has redirected the monopoly of literature towards the virtual, a long text can cause a readership to retreat. In this context, choosing the short story is a must thanks to its relatable themes and the impact of its characters.

The intention here has been both to reveal everything Moone Nda’a’s text says and also how it says it. While the novel and other genres prioritise noble themes, the short story is content with everyday themes that are sometimes trivial or anecdotal. However, it is important to remove any ambiguity concerning the notion of theme, which can be confused with that of

subject. While Pierre Brunel states that “the theme is a subject of concern and general interest for man” (Brunel, Pichois and Rousseau 1983), not all subjects are themes. The subject only becomes a theme when it has general, universal, abstract and experimental significance. Thus, the choice of everyday themes helps anchor the story in reality, and makes it appeal to the empathy of readers. Abuse, rape and assault are everyday themes. And we see them in “La révolte de Mbazoua”.

A whole “specialist” vulgar lexicon strengthens the thematic field of rape along with related motifs (abuse and assault, violence, etc.): “*raboter*” (screwing) – “screwing kids in their offices” (Nda’a 2020, 9); “*prédateur*” (predatorial) – “predatorial moves” (ibid., 14); “*sexe*” (sex) – “partial to sex”; “*sans élégance ni courtoisie*” (with neither elegance nor courtesy) (ibid., 14); “*abusaient*” (abused) – “abused them” (ibid., 14); “*imbus d’eux-mêmes*” (full of themselves) (ibid., 14); “*viola*” (raped/violated) – “he raped her ... and, each time, he left the same threatening behaviour to linger upon her” (ibid., 17); “*violeraït*” – “he would not violate or compromise a girl’s destiny” (ibid., 19). The language is crude and peppered with Cameroonisms – indeed, the reader needs to engage with Moone Nda’a’s language register to understand that “*fesse*” (arse) refers to a woman’s genitals, or that “*panthère*” (panther) means “prostitute”, and that “*raboter*” refers to rough sex, as hard as a carpenter’s plane on wood – and it witnesses the reality of a widely discussed occurrence at the University of Yaoundé I. In this regard, Moone Nda’a informs us that Professor Ndingo is suspended following the rape of Mbazoua and many other students. Indeed, he highlights that “a proposal for a five-year suspension from all academic duties and activities would be submitted to the top brass. Mbazoua also takes him to court” (ibid., 20). Indeed, this information evokes the four-year suspension of a lecturer¹⁶ at the University of Yaoundé I. The formal charges brought against him by one of the students he supervised in the fifth year¹⁷ are the same as detailed above. The following extract reveals the content of a recording of Professor Ndingo’s words to Mbazoua (and, conveniently, they closely resemble those of the aforementioned lecturer): “Your university life depends on me; if you don’t give me your *fesses*, you’ll never graduate. I’ll never write your pre-viva report” (ibid., 19). So now let’s read an extract from another audio recording, this time by the student of the incriminated teacher at the University of Yaoundé I (who provided a fatal testimony leading to his suspension): “Your *fesses* just kill me; that’s what I want ... I’m going to rape you even ... go fuck those rules and regulations of yours.” Broadcasting the audio on social networks attracted even more attention. Mbazoua broadcasts it on “Nouvelles Ndolè” radio station

(ibid., 19), while the student at Yaoundé I had the audio played on Sky One Radio.¹⁸ And that's not all. Professor Ndingo's court case is similar to that brought by the lecturer at Yaoundé I¹⁹ against the supervised student and journalist responsible for the broadcast.

Hence, themes are once again under the spotlight by drawing attention back to individual rights and freedoms. And don't forget that African puritanism considers these themes to be taboo. Therefore, by making them the cornerstone of his stories, Nda'a confronts this dual value system.

Character Effects and the Sympathy System

Vincent Jouve (1998) explains how the short story creates a particular reading effect. So, when we read a story, we personally experience an effect: Moone Nda'a's characters are introduced as the framework for the anticipatory game on which the reading is based. When we read, we are also tempted to imagine the rest of the text before we reach the end of the story. Preparing the reader to construct possible narratives is common to all short stories.

Further, the person effect comes into play when the author produces a referential illusion by generating a "truth" by attributing proper nouns to his characters, by evoking an interior life, by creating structures of suspense, an illusion of autonomy, factual context, authenticity of the stories told, etc.

Finally, the person effect serves as a pretext for readers. It becomes an excuse for them to enter a scene or text phantasmagorically (for example, "sexually obsessed" readers take the place of Professor Ndingo against Mbazoua, or vice versa for Ndingo's adversaries), hence there is a choice of three types of concupiscence:²⁰ *libido sentiendi* or sexual desire, materialised by Professor Ndingo and all those who, like him, believe that rape indicates the satisfaction of an insalubrious desire; *libido sciendi* or the desire to reveal all, to transgress the forbidden and censorship; and *libido dominandi* or a passion for power.

A sympathy system comes into play when the text privileges the person effect. It distinguishes between three codes:

- **The narrative code:** Readers identify with the figure occupying the same position as them (according to knowledge or aspirations). The activation of this code depends on

the reception each reader grants this collection. Generally, victims like Mbazoua develop this code while rapists like Professor Ndingo do the opposite.

- **The emotional code:** This is no longer about readers' knowledge but about their knowledge of a character; the more we know about someone, the more we worry about what happens to them. For example, Tatisong's initial long trip to America, his run of bad luck and the conversations with his wife about his past informing his journey could attract the attention of readers who share the same experience of immigration.
- **The cultural code:** This is based on the readers' values. If the short story is culturally relatable, it becomes an ideological vehicle for readers and not a purely aesthetic subject. Thus, *La révolte de Mbazoua* could have real success in the Cameroonian academic or intellectual world – more than in the West, for example. It thus, first and foremost, reaches out to Cameroonian readers by using the same register as them, the same examples from their daily lives.

Conclusion

The main objective of this analysis was to identify devices Moone Nda'a uses in his short stories to condemn the failings of Cameroonian university campuses as well as their social impact, employing theoretical and methodological propositions from Lahaie, Rabau, Lord and more. By exposing universities, he has opened our eyes to this sanctuary of knowledge eroded by amoral abuses. The use of referential illusions through the inclusion of real places, credible character names and common stories strengthens the social agenda of an author who wishes to appear moralistic, critical and didactic. For him, the short story becomes the writing of a traumatic experience insofar as J. Roger Kurtz understands it, as explored by Wale Adebani:

Given that modern African literature is a product of the ultimate traumatic experience, namely colonialism – and the centuries of slave trade that preceded it, the other forms of racial subjection that attended and succeeded it (including apartheid), the superpower (ideological) global politics that marginalised and devastated post-independent Africa, and the current globalised neoliberal capital which structurally relegates Africa and fuels a myriad of social, economic and political crises in the continent – it is no surprise that a running theme in the social

reflection of African writers is “the history of fragmentation and violence”.
(Adebanwi 2014, 11)

Moone Nda’a’s works reaffirm the view that this distressing situation has roots in times past. Violence and trauma suffered during colonisation and slavery can explain the violence inflicted today on female students and male and female teaching staff in the African university system. *La révolte de Mbazoua* is a very rich work providing a literary counterpart to real, contemporary experiences, extending an invitation to improve the condition of university life, escaping silence to express freedom of thought without critical praise.

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References

- Adebanwi, Wale. 2014. *Writers and Social Thought in Africa*. London: Routledge.
- Barthes, Roland. 1973. “Théorie du texte.” *Encyclopaedia Universalis*.
<https://www.universalis.fr/encyclopedie/theorie-du-texte/>.
- Barthes, Roland. 1981. “Theory of the Text.” In *Untying the Text: A Post-Structuralist Reader*, edited by Robert Young, 31–47. London: Routledge.
- Brunel, Pierre, Claude Pichois, and André-Michel Rousseau. 1983. *Qu’est-ce que la littérature comparée?* Paris: Armand Colin.
- Genette, Gérard. 1972. *Figure III*. Paris: Éditions du Seuil.
- Gordimer, Nadine. 2010. “The Short Story in Africa.” In *Telling Times: Writing and Living, 1950–2008*, 168–173. London: Bloomsbury.
- Hamon, Philippe. 1977. “Pour un statut sémiologique du personnage.” In *Poétique du récit*, edited by Roland Barthes et al., 115–180. Paris: Éditions du Seuil.

- Husserl, Edmund. 1970. *The Crisis of European Sciences and Transcendental Phenomenology: An Introduction to Phenomenological Philosophy*. Evanston: Northwestern University Press.
- Jokeng, Albert Jiatsa. 2015. *La Condition de l'enseignant vacataire*. Paris: L'Harmattan.
- Jouve, Vincent. 1998. *L'Effet-personnage dans le roman*. Paris: PUF.
- Kane, Mohamadou. 1983. *Roman Africain et tradition*. Dakar: NEA.
- Kiguru, Doseline. 2020. "Genre versus Prize: The Short Story Form and African Oral Traditions." *English in Africa* 47 (3): 37–54.
- Kurtz, J. Roger. 2014. "Literature, Trauma, and the African Moral Imagination." *Journal of Contemporary African Studies* 32: 421–435.
- Lahaie, Christiane. 1998. "La Nouvelle: Théories et pratiques de l'écriture." *Québec Français* 108: 62–64.
- Lord, Michel. 1993. "La forme narrative brève: genre fixe ou genre flou? Prolégomènes à un projet de recherche sur la pratique Québécoise." In *La Nouvelle: écriture(s) et lecture (s)*, edited by Agnès Whitfield and Jacques Cotman, 49–61. Glendon: GREF/XYZ.
- Maingueneau, Dominique. 1996. *Les termes clés de l'analyse du discours*. Paris: Éditions du Seuil.
- Mura-Brunel, Aline. 2004. *Silences du roman. Balzac et le romanesque contemporain*. Amsterdam: Rodopi.
- Nda'a, Moone. 2020. *La révolte de Mbazoua et autres nouvelles*. Yaoundé: Éditions Ifrikiya.
- Rabau, Sophie. 2002. *L'Intertextualité*. Paris: Flammarion.
- Saint Augustine. 2003. *Confessions*. London: Penguin.
- Van Gorp, Hendrick et al. 2005. *Dictionnaire des termes littéraires*. Paris: Honoré Champion.

Wounfa, Jean-Marie. 2016. "L'Écrivain intellectuel et le destin de l'université camerounaise." *Présence Francophone: Revue de Langue et de Littérature* 86 (1).

¹ The Easterly Wind refers to the huge wave of democracy that swept the African continent after the fall of the Berlin Wall on 9 November 1989 along with the reunification of the two Germanys (FDR and GDR).

² In *The Crisis of European Sciences and Transcendental Phenomenology*, Husserl defines the Lebenswelt (lifeworld) as "the general ground of human existence in this world" and as "this world in which we live" (1970).

³ Other theories that do not feature here could be explored; as Mohamadou Kane says, "no method, no framework can be sufficient and, once and for all, cast a dazzling light upon the profound structures of literary works" (1983, 21).

⁴ Rabau invites us to "envisage [literature] as a space or network, a library if you like, where each text transforms the others and in return, they modify it" (2002, 15).

⁵ *La révolte de Mbazoua et autres nouvelles* is an 87-page collection of short stories by Moone Nda'a, published in 2020 by Éditions Ifrikiya. The book engages readers, making them aware of the ills that imperceptibly sully everyday life, immersing them in the author's peregrinations around Cameroonian universities as well as exploring the so-called "Anglophone" conflict (in the short story "La Bataille des vignes du Koupé-Manengouba" (The Battle of Koupé-Manengouba Vines)) and exploring hospital life ("L'Histoire de Virginie Kouémi" (The Story of Virginie Kouémi)).

⁶ Indeed, those in charge of universities (with their potentially corrupt infrastructures) make the excuse that not just anyone can teach in them, and if a temporary worker is entrusted to do so then that is already worth more than a wage, for not only can they parade around the district like a university lecturer, but they can also acquire real-life didactic experience.

⁷ There is a playfulness in this naming, since some descriptions refer to Université Yaoundé I, where the author studied. This specific reference to the Université de Maroua could be explained by the fact that the author, Moone Nda'a, teaches in that institution.

⁸ However, the names of characters have been changed.

⁹ Moone Nda'a is the pseudonym of Roger Fopa.

¹⁰ Some people publish informally (with unknown publishers, self-publishers, dummy publishers, etc.) to such an extent that the government can no longer control publishing ahead of time.

¹¹ NST is the acronym for “Notes Sexuellement Transmissibles” (Sexually Transmitted Grades).

¹² This is according to the current salary scale for Cameroonian civil servants, pertaining to the grade and level of each individual.

¹³ An exception can be made for the following powerful depiction, which aims to strengthen the density of events Mbazoua will experience: “Mbazoua was truly a special girl. She had long salt and pepper hair, despite her 23 years, giving her an allure. She looked like an Arab Choa. Her perfectly average waist was transformed by the uniform fullness of her curves and boosted by her graceful walk, making her young body look like that of an experienced woman. Her subdued feline eyes raised by her prominent cheekbones and chocolate complexion evoked for him a villager’s naivety. Her teeth, enhanced by sparkling enamel, lit up her face and added devastating spice to her charm. Her smile could simply kill. She was born to be beautiful and to please” (Nda’a 2020, 11).

¹⁴ In “Pour un statut sémiologique du personnage” (For a Semiological Status of the Character), Philippe Hamon (1977) reveals that characters in a story are recognised by their hierarchical importance in terms of qualification (studied through the quantity and nature of features attributed to a character: injury, scars, laugh, face, twitch), distribution (referring to the number of times a character appears and where in the story these appearances take place – for example, strategic places like the start or finish of a chapter), autonomy (shown through the independence of a character, their freedom to act, personal decisions), functionality (the hero carries out certain important acts, encounters obstacles that they overcome or not, etc.), conventional pre-designation (youth, courage, solitude, stubbornness – in short, a certain codification that supplies characteristics according to the genre of text, such as picaresque novel, *chanson de geste*, crime fiction, short story, etc.), and the narrator’s explicit commentary.

¹⁵ These include video games, smartphones, televisions, the internet and social networks.

¹⁶ This is a well-known true story that is available online and on social media. His name is not published here as we do not have permission to do so.

¹⁷ This occurred on the Diplôme de Professeur de l'Enseignement Secondaire, 2ème grade (Secondary School Teachers' Diploma, grade 2).

¹⁸ Sky One Radio is a private radio station in Cameroon.

¹⁹ To our knowledge, these proceedings were unsuccessful.

²⁰ This Latin term, which derives from “*cupere*” (to desire), comes from Saint Augustine, who, employing the theories of Plato, highlighted three separate stages of concupiscence in his autobiographical text *Confessions* (Saint Augustine 2003).